

The Impacts of Insecurity and Instability on FDI Inflow and Business Activities in Afghanistan

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Abstract: Despite the existence of plenteous investment opportunities in various sectors such as mining, infrastructure, energy, agriculture, services, construction, and telecommunication, moreover the unprecedented attention of the international community, large-scale financial assistance in the last two decades, the strong support and significant reforms initiated by the government to facilitate a better environment for doing business; unfortunately, Afghanistan remains one of the most unattractive poor economies in the world. Four decades of conflicts, the deterrent security situation, and the political instability significantly caused backwardness and poverty and negatively impacted the overall economic growth in the country.

Therefore, this study investigates the negative impacts of insecurity and instability on the inflow of foreign direct investments (FDI) and business activities in Afghanistan. Meanwhile, it explores the role of FDI and business activities in stimulating economic growth, improving security conditions, and assuring peace and stability in the country.

The research employed a survey questionnaire to collect the primary data from the Afghan business community who have been directly and indirectly affected by the consequences of insecurity and instability. At the same time, the literature of other studies was comprehensively reviewed to discuss the research topic and collect the secondary data. A mixture of qualitative and quantitative approaches was adopted to analyze and describe the research findings.

Keywords: Afghan Economy, Business Activities, Economic Growth, FDI, Insecurity and FDI, Instability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The economic, political, and environmental conditions are directly tied to the decline and increase in foreign direct investments (FDI) and business activities. Studies explain that economic factors such as GDP growth, trade openness, market size, regulatory framework, human capital, and infrastructure have always influenced the inflow of FDI and the enhancement of business activities in many countries. But with more extensive studies, it was found that in addition to economic factors, non-economic factors also affect the business activities and the level of FDI inflow in some post-conflict and conflicting countries. Non-economic factors such as political stability, security, the rule of law and order, investment guarantee schemes, property rights, good governance, supportive legislation, etc., play a progressive role. In contrast, factors such as the existence of insecurity, insurgency, terrorism, corruption in the administrative system, mafia system, ethnic, national, regional, and cultural disagreements, and political instability play a deterrent role in FDI inflow and overall business activities in the country.

This study explores the negative impacts of insecurity, instability, insurgencies and terrorism on FDI inflow, business activities and overall economy of Afghanistan during the last two decades.

1.1 Problem Statement

When we look at Afghanistan's case, favorable policies, incentive packages, and administrative reforms are not enough to stimulate investments and business activities by the private sector; what is more important is the assurance of safety and security for private businesses that result in increased profitability and sustainable private sector empowerment.

Despite the existence of tremendous investment opportunities in various sectors such as mining, infrastructure, energy, agriculture, services, construction and telecommunication, moreover the unprecedented attention of the international community, large-scale financial assistance in the last two decades, the strong support and significant reforms initiated by the government to facilitate a better environment for doing business; unfortunately, Afghanistan remains one of the backward and poor countries, and in the worst state of its political-economic history. The deterrent security situation and the lack of lasting and durable peace are considered among the key factors for backwardness, widespread poverty, and, finally, the negative trend in the country's investment growth and development.

One of the most significant obstacles for private sector activists, especially for foreign and domestic investors, despite the investment outputs, is the existence of high levels of threats and risks. That is why, in recent years, with the intensification of war and insurgency, the amount of investments in particular FDI has been very small and insignificant. The existing investments in the country are not progressing smoothly; some of the large investments are on hold due to the insecurity and instability being the major reasons.

The private sector is the prime victim of insecurity and instability in Afghanistan. On an annual basis, private businesses incur millions of dollars of losses due to the terrorist attacks and bombings in commercial areas. Moreover, political instability and weak rule of law in the country lead to increased criminal activities such as kidnapping, robbery and murder, which severely threaten business people and their investments and cause an increase in the cost of doing business and impact profitability. In the presence of such an unpleasant environment, the private sector is discouraged from engaging in business activities in the country, and instead, they look for opportunities in other countries that facilitate a safer and better investment climate.

This study aims to explore the main consequences of insecurity and instability that discourage FDI inflow and the expansion of business activities in Afghanistan. Furthermore, the study also investigates the role of FDI and business activities in economic growth, employment generation, poverty alleviation, and, more importantly, the improvement of security conditions in Afghanistan.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 FDI and Its Advantages

There are different definitions of FDI, and they change depending on the investment objectives and purpose. According to World Bank, FDI is a kind of investment in which foreign capital flows to a country other than the investor's home country. For this investment to be classified as foreign direct investment, the foreign investor must hold 10% or more of the local firm, get a significant interest in a worldwide corporation, or establish a subsidiary in a foreign country [1].

Foreign direct investments provide numerous advantages for the development of the host country. According to Al-Irniani, FDI is a major driver of economic growth in developing countries. It increases the country's foreign exchange reserves while ensuring investments within the economy. FDI has the dynamic potential to enable capital arrangements, transfer contemporary technology and expertise, and create job opportunities, which are critical needs for developing countries and positively affect economic growth [2]. According to Saggi, FDI empowers the host country's economy by enhancing local production, boosting exports and increasing international trade [3]

2.2. Factors Affecting the FDI inflow

There have been numerous researches and empirical studies on factors affecting FDI and business activities in developing and post-conflict countries. These factors may vary from country to country due to the different socio-cultural and political aspects. Some key economic factors include liberal policies, incentive packages, administrative reforms, tax preferences, investment guarantee schemes, technology advancement, modern infrastructure, market size, high GDP growth, low-interest rates, low inflation rates, stable exchange rate, etc. that encourage FDI inflow [4, 5]

GDP plays an important role in attracting inward FDI. An empirical study conducted by Panigrahi and Panda [6] explores that GDP is the main common factor attracting FDI inflow in three Asian countries, namely China, Malaysia, and India.

Similarly, many studies have explored the influence of exchange rate fluctuations on the FDI inflow. The findings of an empirical analysis of firm-level data on US foreign direct investments to South Korea show that FDI inflows have a substantial relationship with real and projected exchange rate fluctuations [7]. Market size is also among the key economic factors that stimulate FDI inflow in the host country. Mughal and Akram [8] employed an error correction model to investigate the influence of market size on FDI inflows in Pakistan. This study analysed time-series data from 1984 to 2008, and the findings revealed that market size has a positive effect on the inflow of foreign direct investments to developing countries.

Furthermore, many studies have investigated the positive effect of strong infrastructure on FDI inflow. The effects of infrastructure, particularly telecommunication, energy, and transportation infrastructure, on FDI in Cameroon have been investigated by Mbiankeu using time series data from 1984-to 2014. The findings clearly illustrate the positive effect of infrastructure on FDI inflow [9]. More importantly, the regulatory environment in the host country plays a critical role in the attraction of FDI and the enhancement of business activities. Many studies show that an unfavourable regulatory environment with restrictions significantly discourages FDI and overall business activities by the private sector. The findings of the studies conducted by some researchers explore that unfriendly regulatory framework and poor governance [10]; policies in the host country that restrict the remittance of profit and the repatriation of capital to the home country, limit ownership in the shares of the investment and restrict trade and FDI [11]; and the government regulations that impose restriction on holding equity by foreigners [12] are all the factors that have negative impacts on the flow of FDI and the business activities by the private sector.

2.2.1 The Consequences of Insecurity and Instability

In conflicting countries like Afghanistan, in addition to the economic factors discussed above, some non-economic factors serve as challenges and highly discourage the flow of investments and business activities. Insecurity and instability resulting from conflicts are among the most significant obstacles to economic growth and development. The literature in many studies postulates a consensus that security plays a vital role in sustainable socio-economic development and national welfare. Oladeji and Florunso consider national security as a prerequisite; indeed, a *sin qua non*, for any country's growth and economic development, and the efforts for any kind of development can be wiped out in the presence of insecurity [13]. According to Blattman and Miguel, insecurity and war impact a country's development in many ways. It includes the reduction of business activities, the slowdown in investments, the loss of physical capital and fall in output and a drop in consumer demand; miss-allocation of manpower from production to protection, and the shift in government spending from the social sector toward military sector; disruption of the labor market; the weakening of political and socio-economic institutions which manage the economy and the destruction of infrastructure in the country [14, 15]. In a study on the relationship between insecurity and socio-economic development in Nigeria, Ewetan explored that the rising level of insecurity in the country between 2007 and 2012 has retarded economic development and caused the slowdown of FDI inflow and reduction of business activities [16].

In Afghanistan's case, the intensification of insecurity, insurgency, and political instability caused a substantial drop in the country's economic growth. According to World Bank [17], the GDP growth drastically declined from 12.7% in 2012 to 2.9 % in 2019, leading to an increase in poverty and unemployment. Furthermore, a significant outflow of capital and withdrawal of investments from Afghanistan have particularly started in 2014 (right after the withdrawal of NATO forces) onward. According to data registered by the Afghanistan Centre of Business Registration (ACBR), the annual FDI declined from \$170 million in 2015 to \$1.7 million (excluding the 4th quarter) in 2019 [18]. On the other hand, the annual Bottleneck surveys of the Afghanistan Chamber of Commerce and Investment (ACCI) on the business climate clearly indicate the deterioration of security conditions in the country between 2015 -2019. Thus, the survey reports verify that the decline in annual FDI and the economic growth is mainly due to the intensification of security problems and political instability, which negatively impacted the investors' confidence in the country [19]. Furthermore, according to Jahanmal, a significant outflow of capital and withdrawal of investments from Afghanistan have particularly started from 2014 (right after the withdrawal of NATO forces) onward. Businesses have blamed "insecurity and the lack of investment facilities" as major reasons for the failure to attract direct and indirect foreign investments [20].

Considering the above discussions, no investor, whether foreigner or local, would be interested in doing business in countries with no safety and high business risks due to security problems. Economic globalization has facilitated tremendous opportunities in terms of the business environment in different parts of the world. Therefore, investors prefer countries where their investments are safe and protected, ensuring higher business profitability.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA ANALYSIS

3.1 Research Design and Model

This study is a descripto-exploratory research where the existing variables are explored and some relevant data is collected to verify the relations between the variables. Thus, a mixture of deductive and inductive approach, which is mostly compatible with the nature of the study, is chosen to identify the correlations between the variables. Furthermore, the research is based on a combination of quantitative and qualitative research design. According to Bryman [21], combined qualitative and quantitative findings help to forge an overall or negotiated account of the results, which is not possible by using a singular approach. Combined designs can also help to identify the similarities and differences between particular aspects of a phenomenon [22]. According to Creswell [23], the mixed method serves as a means for seeking convergence across quantitative and qualitative designs in social science researches.

The research model investigates the negative impacts of insecurity and instability on FDI inflow and the enhancement of business activities. Thus, we emphasized how changes in independent variables (Insecurity and Instability) would affect the dependent variables (FDI and Business activities). The study also explores the influence of dependent variables on overall economic growth, improvement of security conditions, and sustainment of peace and stability in the country.

3.2 Data Collection Methodology

In this research we used both primary and secondary sources to collect data. The secondary data was retrieved through a literature review of the academic articles, books, reports, online documents and papers. Whereas, the primary data was gathered using a survey questionnaire filled by 130 participants from the Afghan business community. According to Singleton and Strait [24], surveys are the most commonly used data collection tools in social science researches, because surveys explore and explain the human behaviour.

A survey questionnaire consisting of six main questions was developed and used to conduct the survey. The same questionnaire was prepared both in English and Dari. The English version was directly uploaded to the online survey platform (surveyMonkey.com) which is the commonly used platform, and the link was shared with the respondents. At the same time, the Dari questionnaire was used for telephone interviews and filled manually, later on, it was translated into English and merged to the online survey. Almost 80 % of the respondents who had access to the internet were approached and received the link for the online survey through mediums such as Email, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, and Skype whereas the remaining 20% were approached via phone calls and filled the questionnaire with the help of the interviewer.

The questions were mainly focused on the impact of insecurity on the investments and business activities of the respondents. Their views and perspectives on how the insecurity is hindering FDI and the expansion of businesses were investigated. Moreover, the respondents were also asked about the influence of FDI inflow on certain factors such as employment generation, encouraging private sector, poverty alleviation, increase in public revenue, and export promotion.

3.2.1 Target Population and Sample Sizing

According to Bhattacharjee [25], "target population" refers to a large group of people or individuals from which researchers want to gather information and generalize the inferences. The population encompasses the entire group of people, items, organizations and the country that the researcher intends to conduct a scientific study about.

In this study, the target population was the Afghan private sector members who have been directly and indirectly impacted by the consequences of insecurity and instability. They all have officially registered businesses functioning under the umbrella of Afghanistan Chamber of Commerce and Investment (ACCI). At the same time, they represent medium and large-scale industries. Most of them are capable of making considerable investments at national and international levels and contribute significantly to the country's economic growth. Therefore, a total of 250 members of ACCI who had access to emails and internet were selected as the target population for this research.

In this study, we mainly used non-probability sampling techniques with more focus on convenience sampling. As per Matthews and Ross [26] a convenience sampling technique is applied in researches where the researcher has limited time and resources and can select the samples based on convenience and ease of access. Thus, considering the limited time and resources, we choose the sample which was easily accessible and ready to participate in the survey and willing to respond.

Using the below equation a sample size of 130 participants out of 250 target population were selected to be surveyed for data collection:

$$n = z^2 * p * (1 - p) / e^2$$

$$n \text{ (with finite population correction)} = [z^2 * p * (1 - p) / e^2] / [1 + (z^2 * p * (1 - p) / (e^2 * N))]$$

Where N (Population Size) = 250, Z (Confidence level) = 1.645, e (Margin of Error) = 0.05, and P (Sample Proportion – uncertain) = 0.5.

As shown in Figures 1 and 2, the sample has been classified into two categories such as 1) Business Sectors in which the respondents are active and 2) Business Locations (Geography) where the main businesses of the respondents are located. Business Sectors are mainly chosen based on their contributions to the country’s economy. As per National Statistics and Information Authority of Afghanistan (NSIA) [27], sectors such as services, trade, manufacturing (Industry) and construction are the ones in which most of the investments and business activities are carried out during the last two decades, and they have significant shares in the country’s GDP; therefore, these sectors are dominantly represented in the sample. As far as the business locations are concerned, the majority of medium and large-scale businesses are located in the capital city of Kabul and four zonal provinces of the country such as Balkh, Herat, Nangarhar, and Kandahar. Therefore, we have more respondents from Kabul and zonal provinces. Some of the foreign companies doing business in Afghanistan have also participated in the survey, and their business locations are shown as Kabul and the city in their home countries. In consideration of the above reasons and to ensure an accurate and reliable data collection, this sample was chosen to be surveyed.

Fig. 1: Business Sectors of the Respondents

Fig. 2: Business Locations of the Respondents

3.3 Data Analysis and Findings

In order to be in line with the nature of the study, a mixture of qualitative and quantitative data is collected using secondary sources through a survey questionnaire. The questionnaire contained mixed types of questions to avoid any biases and collect accurate information relevant to the research objectives. There was a combination of ranking, list, open-ended and close-ended questions.

The data provided by the respondents clearly indicates the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The survey also identified the respondents' viewpoints and perceptions of how the FDI inflow and business activities stimulate economic growth and ensure the maintenance of a peaceful and stable business environment in the country.

3.3.1 Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics give straightforward information about the observations and about the sample that has been interpreted after the collection of data. It is applied for displaying the data or numerical facts in any form, such as a table or graph, and with the procedure of examining and determining the data. It gathers and compiles a wide range of data and knowledge in a significant and organized way. It is a simple method that can easily convert the outcomes to frequency, overall averages, and percentages.

In this study, the researcher utilizes descriptive statistics to analyse data and describe the findings of the data collection process. The graphical analysis is produced to indicate the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Furthermore, to better understand the respondents' answers, a simple percentage analysis is applied and an accumulated summary of the findings is provided. The descriptive analysis of the findings for each questions are illustrated with the help of diagrams as below:

Question 1. *How do you evaluate the impacts of insecurity and instability on your business?*

Results: As shown in Figure 3, question 1 is a multiple-choice list question that has been answered by all 130 respondents. The analysis shows that 62% of the respondents believe that the impact of insecurity on their business is extremely negative, and 38% believe the impact is negative, whereas only 1% thinks insecurity has no impact on their business activities.

Fig. 3: The results of Question 1

Question 2. *How do you see the impacts of insecurity and instability on Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) inflow to Afghanistan?*

Results: As shown in Figure 4, similar to the first question, the second question is also a multiple-choice list question type. All 130 respondents answered this question, and the analysed result illustrates that 69% of the respondents believe insecurity is a big hurdle for FDI inflow, and the impact is extremely negative. Respectively 30% believe that the impact of insecurity on the attraction of FDI is negative, whereas only 1% believe insecurity has no impact on FDI attraction.

Fig. 4: The results of Question 2

The results of both question 1 and 2 confirm that there is a significant inverse relationship between insecurity (independent variable) and FDI inflow and business Activities (Dependent variables).

Question 3. *If you think that insecurity is hindering FDI inflow and business activities in Afghanistan, please briefly write your views on how it hinders?*

Results: Question 3 is an open-ended question that inquires the respondents' viewpoints and opinions on how the insecurity hinders FDI inflow and business activities. 117 out of 130 respondents have answered this question and briefly explained their views in the comment box. The most common findings among the provided answers are as follows:

- Insecurity causes political instability and negatively impacts investors' confidence.
- In an insecure environment, the risk of doing business increases, and the business environment becomes unattractive.
- Insecurity directly threatens investors and their investments. It increases the rate of criminal activities such as kidnapping, robbery and murder, which becomes a direct threat for the family members of the investors and business people.
- Insecurity impacts profitability and increases the cost of doing business. It also causes double taxation imposed by the insurgents.
- Insecurity is a driving factor for corruption, and it significantly hinders administrative reforms.
- Insecurity encourages the capital outflow and migration of skilled labor out of the country.
- Foreign investors are significantly discouraged from investing in an insecure environment where there is a high risk of doing business.
- War and insecurity destroy the infrastructure in the country and hinder growth and development.

The results of this question clarify that, insecurity is a big hurdle for investments and business activities in Afghanistan. Therefore, investors and the private sector are reluctant to invest and expand their business activities in Afghanistan.

Question 4. *Please rank the role of FDI on the below areas, grading from 1 (the least) to 5 (the most).*

Results: As shown in Figure 5, question 4 is a ranking question type that has been answered by 126 respondents. This question investigates the influence of FDI (as the independent variable) on a series of economic factors (as dependent variables). The analysis of the results shows that FDI influences all factors illustrated in Figure 4. In particular, it more likely encourages the expansion of business activities in the country and as well as contributes to the public revenue increase through tax payments and royalties.

Fig. 5: The results of Question 4

Question 5. Do you think FDI inflow and enhanced business activities ensure sustainable peace and political stability in Afghanistan?

Results: As shown in Figure 6, question 5 is a close-ended question that has been answered by all 130 participants. The question inquires the influence of FDI on maintaining a long-lasting peace and political stability. In this context, FDI is an independent variable, whereas peace and stability are dependent variables. The analysed results illustrate that 85% of the respondents believe FDI ensures peace and stability. In contrast, 15% think there is no proportional relation between FDI and peace and stability.

Fig. 6: The results of Question 5

Question 6: Have you ever missed business/investment opportunities due to security problems in Afghanistan? If yes, please tick one or all of the below options.

Results: This question is a multiple-answer question that has been answered by all 130 respondents. The question investigates a series of opportunities the businesses missed due to the security problems in the country. As shown in Figure N, the analysis of the results indicates that insecurity impacted all the areas listed in question 6. But, there were more complaints about the two factors which are directly related to FDI inflow. 67% of the respondents complained about the challenges of low profitability and high cost of doing business. Respectively, 58% of the respondents complained about difficulties in attracting foreign business partners.

Fig. 7: The results of Question 6

4. CONCLUSION

The research findings eventually confirmed that insecurity and instability are the leading causes of a sluggish economy and shrinking investment growth and business enhancement in Afghanistan. Economic growth and development in an environment with no security and stability are undoubtedly inconceivable. As highlighted in the literature review, many studies conducted in different countries explored how insecurity and instability impact business profitability and incur unbearable losses for private investments and, therefore, considerably hinder FDI inflow and business activities. Likewise, our survey results indicated that private sector investments and businesses are drastically suffering from the consequences of insecurity; therefore, they are highly discouraged from doing business in Afghanistan. The business community believes that unrest and insecurity lead to uncertainty and ambiguity, resulting in a lack of confidence. In a turbulent and unstable environment, the cost of doing business increases due to unnecessary expenditures, double taxation, administrative corruption resulting from the weak rule of law, and business profitability is negatively impacted. Meanwhile, the increased criminal activities such as kidnapping, robbery, and murder directly threaten the investors and their families, leaving them with no choice other than allocating unnecessary additional expenses for more stringent security maintenance. Furthermore, the flow of millions of dollars and the migration of skilled labor out of the country were mainly due to the absence of a peaceful and secure environment and employment opportunities. All the above obstacles lead to an unattractive environment with high risks of doing business, discouraging foreign investors, and blocking FDI inflow to Afghanistan.

As explained in the first chapter, the objectives set in this research were to investigate the impacts of insecurity and instability on the attraction of FDI and the expansion of business activities. Meanwhile, we aimed to discover how increased FDI and enhanced business activities will result in economic growth and assurance of a peaceful environment through job creation and poverty alleviation. Looking at the findings of the study and survey results, the objectives we set for our research have been adequately met, and the relationship between the variables is proved to be significant. The

analyzed results clarify that security is a primary building block for economic development and national welfare in a society. In an unsafe and unstable environment, the investors would not be interested in investing and starting their business activities.

The findings also confirmed that FDI inflow brings new opportunities and helps to generate employment, reduce poverty, increase household incomes, bring new capital and remove the balance of payment constraints, and stimulate the expansion of business activities and export promotion. More importantly, FDI and enhanced business activities reciprocally contribute to improving security conditions and assure long-lasting peace and stability.

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